

DECONSTRUCTING AUGMENTED VISION FUNCTIONALITY

Version 2

Description

To facilitate the responsible and meaningful uptake of AR technologies in professional areas, the project goal is to thoroughly investigate how the human visual system operates in augmented 3D environments displayed via near-eye displays, and its relation to user performance and comfort with a specific focus on professional implementation, which will facilitate further technological advancements based on better understanding of augmented vision functionality.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Deconstruction augmented
vision functionality (Izp-2024/1-
0201)

Researchers

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Organizations
University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [DECONSTRUCTING AUGMENTED VISION FUNCTIONALITY](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#)

Grants: [Deconstruction augmented vision functionality \(Izp-2024/1-0201\)](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date:

4. Templates

Descriptions

Visual functions in AR

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of the data collection/generation is to investigate how the human visual system operates in augmented 3D environments displayed via near-eye AR headsets, particularly multifocal displays. This data will help assess the relationship between visual perception, user performance, and comfort, addressing individual differences in AR image processing. The findings will contribute to the development of evidence-based guidelines for optimizing AR technology in professional applications ensuring safe and effective implementation.

The data originates from controlled experiments involving participants with varying visual abilities. It includes objective measurements of eye accommodation, vergence, and pupil size, user performance metrics (accuracy, reaction time), and subjective user experience assessments. These data points will be collected using specialized AR headsets, vision assessment tools (e.g., PowerRef 3 photorefractor), and psychophysical testing methods in collaboration with industry partners and research institutions.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Clinical data
- Experimental data
- Observation data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No, existing data will not be used.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The project has a strong and long-term socio-economic impact by facilitating innovations

through human factor research and contributing to the responsible uptake of AR technology in the professional areas, which in the long term contributes to increasing the trust in the innovative technology in society. Namely, the project will foster understanding of augmented vision functionality and factors affecting professional task performance and user experience in 3D environment augmented with digital overlays. This knowledge is important for the responsible and meaningful applications of AR headsets in professional areas. In the future, our findings could have implications across the following major areas:

- Vision care – gaining an understanding of the adaptation processes of the visual system to near-eye displays and AR, including the factors affecting the duration and outcome of this

adaptation. This knowledge will allow to differentiate display users who may have difficulties working in AR and enable the development of targeted vision training programs designed to prepare professionals for regular use of AR headsets.

- Optical engineering and software development – providing important insights into human

factors that should be considered when designing AR technology. Data-based decisions could lead to specific adjustments in the next-generation technologies. For example, our previous research revealed that the arrangement of image planes in solid-state front-view displays with volumetric 3D images could be optimized based on a more accurate understanding of the visual system's needs and limitations (Pladere, 2021).

- Medical education – addressing the gap between current training methods and the innovative approaches required for integrating AR into medical procedures. Traditional training needs to be supplemented with new methods that equip future medical professionals to fully utilize AR headsets (Ursin et al., 2024). A deeper understanding of these technologies will help shape training curriculums to better prepare medical professionals. A broader and more effective integration of AR technologies in professional settings will ultimately benefit both practitioners and patients in the future.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Tatjana Pladere (0000-0002-7120-9755)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

Firewall, Passwords, Physical access control. Data will be stored on the UL Google Drive and on a work computer during and after the project.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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